

Progress Report

1st Quarter of 2025

GLIM-BioData Gateway for Living Data Management

Within the scope of **PNCADAI - Programa Nacional de Ciência Aberta e Dados Abertos de Investigação**

Part of **Medida RE-C05-i08 - Ciência Mais Digital**
do **PRR - Programa de Recuperação e Resiliência**

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1. Progress Monitoring

The implementation of this Research Data Management Centre comprises the following objectives/goals:

- A. Establish BioData.pt as a national reference in the management and valorisation of life and health science data in Portugal.
- B. Promote data sharing and reuse by developing curation guidelines and best practices for research data management.
- C. Implement two strategic use cases:
 - Biodiversity (non-sensitive data): support the annotation and public sharing of biodiversity datasets to monitor the spread of pathogenic bacteria in aquatic environments and assess human health risks;
 - Genomic data (sensitive data): set up a FEGA Portugal helpdesk, support data curation and develop legal and ethical guidelines, including GDPR compliance.
- D. Deliver specialised training in bioinformatics, data management, and data stewardship:
 - ELIXIR-certified trainers;
 - Build a new generation of life and health data stewards.
- E. Develop tailored processes for managing both sensitive and non-sensitive data, ensuring alignment with FAIR principles and Open Science.
- F. Foster interoperability and integration with national and European networks, including the GDI Consortium, ELIXIR, FEGA, and EOSC.
- G. Ensure long-term sustainability through:
 - Impact monitoring (using KPIs, RI-PATHS methodology, and CoARA principles);
 - Strengthening national collaboration;
 - Active participation in European and ESFRI projects.

1.1. Deliverables

Below is an overview of all deliverables and milestones, as well as, their implementation concerning the contractual timetable (Table 1).

Table 1 - Application Timetable vs Execution – Deliverables and Milestones

Activity	Deliverable /Milestone	Estimated schedule	% Execution as of the report date	
			Expected	Actual
Detailed Work Plan	D1.1 - GLIM-BioData Centre Work Plan	9 May 2025	Expected	100
			Actual	100
Implementation and adoption of an institutional policy for research data management and sharing by the centre's institution(s)	D1.5 - Definition of the institutional policy for RDM and sharing	Up to 9 months after the contract start date (October 2025)	Expected	20
			Actual	20
	D1.6 -Implementation and adoption of the institutional policy for RDM and sharing by the GLIM-BioData participant institution(s)	By the end of the contract	Expected	0
			Actual	0
	M1.1 - Roadshow about the GLIM-BioData Centre and the integration in the Consortium-GDI	By the end of the contract	Expected	20
			Actual	20
M1.2 - Roadshow about human-sensitive data and alignment with FEGA	By the end of the contract	Expected	0	
		Actual	0	
M3.1 - Report on outreach activities with FEGA stakeholders	By the end of the contract	Expected	0	
		Actual	0	
Availability of data sets with reuse potential	D2.1 - Curation and datasets availability plan for Non-sensitive Life Data	Up to 9 months after the contract start date(October 2025)	Expected	0
			Actual	0
	D3.1 - Curation and datasets availability plan for Sensitive Life and Health Data	Up to 9 months after the contract start date (September 2025)	Expected	0
			Actual	0
D2.2 - Publication of datasets for Non-sensitive Life Data	By the end of the contract	Expected	0	
		Actual	0	
D3.2 - Publication of datasets for Sensitive Life and Health Data	December 2025	Expected	0	
		Actual	0	

	M2.2 - DMPortal integration in POLEN	July 2025	Expected	30
			Actual	10
	M2.1 - Open-source electronic lab notebook (eLabFTW) implementation	November 2025	Expected	10
			Actual	10
	M3.2 - Standard Operating Procedures for FEAGA Portugal Helpdesk	December 2025	Expected	0
			Actual	0
Training sessions on good research data management practices according to the plan proposed by the proposing entities	D.4.1 - Training sessions on best practices in RDM for Life Data - "Ready4Intensive" Course - 1 Edition	3 and 4 July 2025 in CiiMAR	Expected	30
			Actual	30
	D.4.2 - Training session on best practices in RDM for Life Data - "Ready4Intensive" Course - 2 nd edition	October 2025 at UCoimbra	Expected	0
			Actual	0
	D4.3 - Training Session for Data Stewards - 1st session	7 July 2025 Online	Expected	10
			Actual	10
	D4.4 - Training Session for Data Stewards - 2nd session	17 November 2025 UCIBIO	Expected	0
			Actual	0
	M4.1 - Training on accessing, processing, and curating datasets	22 September 2025 Online	Expected	0
			Actual	0
M4.2 - Training in eLABFTW	28 April 2025 in CiiMAR in collaboration with Centre GDI FAIRway	Expected	100	
		Actual	100	
M4.3 - Training in eLABFTW	22 September in CCMAR	Expected	10	
		Actual	10	
Completion of 100% of the sessions in the proposed plan	By the end of the contract	Expected	14.3	
		Actual	14.3	
Integration and collaboration in a	D5.1 - Integration into the national data stewards	By the end of the contract	Expected	100

national network of data stewards	network to be operated by the Consortium		Actual	100
	M5.3 -Establishment of a core group of data stewards for sensitive life and health data	November 2025	Expected	0
			Actual	0
Participation in the Consortium's coordination activities	D1.7 - Participation in the Consortium-GDI coordination activities (Participation in at least 80% of Consortium meetings)	By the end of the contract	Expected	10
			Actual	10
Providing a public version of the centre's quarterly progress reports	D1.2 - 1st Progress report	13 May 2025	Expected	100
			Actual	100
	D1.3 - 2nd Progress report	10 September 2025	Expected	0
			Actual	0
	D1.4 - Final report	By the end of the contract	Expected	0
			Actual	0
	Information made available every four months	By the end of the contract	Expected	33.3
			Actual	33.3
Centre GDI Impact	M5.1 - Assessment of BioData.pt node and communities services	June 2025	Expected	70
			Actual	80
	M5.2 - Participation in projects promoted by European infrastructures (ESFRI) and/or funded by European funds	By the end of the contract	Expected	25
			Actual	25
	M5.4 - Key Performance Indicators definition and monitorization	By the end of the contract	Expected	10
			Actual	10

As part of the activities carried out during this reporting period, three key deliverables were completed in alignment with the established timeline. These include deliverable

D1.1 - GLIM-BioData Centre Work Plan, which defines the strategic and operational framework for the project; D1.2 - First GLIM-BioData progress report, which provides an overview of the work developed during the first months of implementation; and D5.1 - Integration and collaboration in the Portuguese network of data stewards, which reflects the project's commitment to fostering a strong and active community of data professionals in Portugal. Additionally, the M4.2 milestone was achieved with the successful delivery of a training session on eLabFTW, held on April 28, 2025, at CIIMAR, in partnership with the FAIRway RDM Centre. The session provided researchers, lab technicians, and data managers with practical knowledge on implementing robust data management practices using the eLabFTW open-source electronic lab notebook. This activity supports GLIM-BioData's broader goal of embedding FAIR principles from the earliest stages of the data lifecycle.

1.2. Explanation of Progress and Possible Deviations

During the current reporting period, significant progress was made, with the completion of three key deliverables and one milestone, all in line with the defined schedule. Firstly, the GLIM-BioData Centre Work Plan (D1.1) was finalised, outlining the strategic direction and operational structure of the project. In addition, the present and first progress report (D1.2) was completed, documenting the activities developed and results achieved during the initial implementation phase. Also concluded was D5.1, through the participation of BioData.pt's data steward Miguel Cisneiros in the Portuguese Network of Data Stewards, managed by the Re.Data consortium, which formalises the project's active engagement in the national network of data stewards, strengthening collaborative efforts across institutions. Moreover, milestone M4.2, corresponding to the training session on eLabFTW, was successfully completed on April 28, 2025, at CIIMAR. The session was held in collaboration with the Centre GDI FAIRway, and aimed to equip researchers, lab technicians, and data managers with the skills to implement good data management practices using the open-source electronic lab notebook eLabFTW. This milestone contributes to the broader objective of promoting FAIR principles from the very beginning of the data lifecycle within the GLIM-BioData project.

As part of the GLIM-BioData Work Plan (D1.1), the distribution and scheduling of several deliverables were revised to better reflect the operational needs and resource availability of the consortium. This realignment ensures a more coherent implementation across work packages, resulting in the fact that no deliverables are currently delayed within the timeline.

Since all deliverables expected during this reporting period have been completed within the updated timeline defined in the GLIM-BioData Work Plan (D1.1), no deviations from the project program have been detected. As a result, no justification for delays, nor any mitigation measures or corrective actions are required at this stage. The project is progressing according to plan, and the current implementation pace supports the successful completion of upcoming milestones and deliverables within their respective timeframes.

2. Overall Execution

During the current reporting period (Feb-Apr 2025), 100% of the activities planned for this stage of the GLIM-BioData project were successfully completed, including the conclusion of all scheduled deliverables and the achievement of the associated milestone. In terms of overall project execution, a total of 12.9% of the deliverables/milestones have been completed so far, corresponding to 4 out of 31. We consider this to be a strong start for the project execution, since it effectively began in February, which means the progress achieved reflects just three months of implementation.

As this is the first progress report for the project, the cumulative global execution rate stands, as mentioned above, at 12.9%, based on the completion of 4 out of 31 total deliverables and milestones proposed for the project. This percentage reflects the overall progress made since the beginning of the implementation phase in February 2025.

The operational execution of the GLIM-BioData project is progressing in line with the established timeline, with each WP advancing according to its planned schedule. In WP1 – Coordination and Management, 2 of the 9 proposed deliverables/milestones have been completed, corresponding to an execution rate of approximately 22.2%. Since WP2 – Management of Non-sensitive Life data, has not yet reached any of its schedule deliverables/milestones, no execution will be reported for now. Like WP2, WP3 - Management of Sensitive Life and Health Data has not yet reached any of its schedule deliverables/milestones, no execution will be reported. In WP4 - Training and Capacity Building, an execution rate of 12.5% has been achieved (1 of the 8 proposed deliverables/milestones have been completed). And finally, regarding WP5 – Impact and Sustainability, of the 5 deliverables/milestones present in this WP, 1 has been executed, resulting in a 20% execution rate. Overall, the execution across work packages reflects a steady progress, with no deviations from the project's operational schedule.

As of this reporting period, and as mentioned before, of the 31 deliverables/milestones proposed in the GLIM-BioData project, 4 have already been successfully completed, which corresponds to 12.9% of deliverables/milestones effectively submitted/completed. This value is consistent with the project's implementation timeline and is representative of the constant progress during this initial phase of execution.

Financial Execution

	Total budget until the end of the Project (Values without IVA)	Execution as of the report date
Total Budget for activities	220 200 €	
Human resources and service provision - includes BioData.pt HR, hiring a Data Steward, hiring a SysAdmin and service provision of a DPO	139 000 €	9 000 € (6.5%)
Training actions - Trainers, fee for Train-the-Trainer, and travel and accommodation	15 200 €	600 € (4%)
Events - Technical meeting, All hands, Roadshow, travel and accommodation	18 000 €	3 000 € (16.6%)
Technical Resources - server, workstation and data center maintenance	48 000 €	3085 € (6.4%)

3. Additional Relevant Considerations

The GLIM-BioData project carried out a wide range of coordination, communication, training, and integration activities during this period. The project officially began with the Kick-Off Meeting, held on March 25, 2025, at the University of Minho, bringing together 22 participants from 10 institutions. Working groups helped define the initial priorities across work packages. André Vieira (UMinho), representing the Re.Data consortium, was also present, reinforcing collaboration between national data initiatives. Following this meeting, the GLIM-BioData Work Plan was finalised and submitted under WP1. The document outlines the strategic direction, detailed tasks, expected deliverables, and milestones across all work packages, and serves as a reference for monitoring progress and guiding implementation.

To support the coordination of project activities, two team members were recruited at the end of March: Gil Poiares Oliveira, as Bioinformatician and Systems Administrator, and

Miguel Cisneiros, as the project's Data Steward. These additions have strengthened the project's technical and operational capacity.

A full visual identity for GLIM-BioData was created, including a colour palette (Fig. 1), typography, and official logos (Fig. 2). A dedicated website (Fig. 3) (<https://biodata.pt/glim>) was launched to present information about the project's goals, structure, events, and work packages. To support internal and external communication, a mailing list (glim@lists.biodata.pt) and a Teams group were established. Communication is also supported through BioData.pt's social media channels, and promotional materials such as a flyer and roll-up banner (Fig. 4) have been developed and used in public events. A PowerPoint presentation was also created specifically for use in the GLIM-BioData roadshows, helping ensure consistent and clear communication of the project's goals, structure, and progress to researchers and institutional audiences.

Figure 1 - GLIM-BioData colour palette

Figure 2 - GLIM-BioData official logos

Figure 3 - GLIM-BioData website

Figure 4 - GLIM-BioData flyer and roll-up banner

Three roadshow sessions were organised in 2025 at UCIBIO Porto, UCIBIO NOVA, and CIIMAR, promoting GLIM-BioData’s mission and reinforcing engagement with the BioData.pt community. These events helped raise awareness about data stewardship, FAIR data practices, and the objectives of the GLIM project.

In line with the project’s training and capacity-building goals, the BioData.pt Training Platform held a meeting on March 6, 2025, to define the 2025 training calendar, including training sessions on data stewardship, research data management, and tools such as eLabFTW. The meeting also addressed trainer availability and the importance of Train-the-Trainer certification for ensuring sustainability in training delivery. In this context, the team also defined criteria for the installation of servers for sensitive data management, ensuring compliance with legal, ethical, and technical standards, particularly in preparation for activities under the FEGA Portugal node.

GLIM-BioData actively contributed to national efforts in data stewardship by responding to two key surveys: the “Characterisation of Research Data Management Support

Professionals” and the POLEN survey (by FCT/FCCN). Both initiatives aim to map the roles and needs of professionals involved in research data management in Portugal and contribute to the national strategy for capacity building. The project also promoted dialogue and collaboration with other national RDM centres. The GLIM team met with GBIF Portugal (ISA/ULisboa) and FAIRway (CIIMAR) to align objectives, exchange best practices, and explore synergies in the context of the GDI Consortium.

On March 26, 2025, BioData.pt led a roundtable at the Bioinformatics Open Days, titled “Research Data Management Centres for Living Data: Driving Open Science and Innovation”. The session brought together representatives from FAIRway, GBIF, and GLIM-BioData and focused on the promotion of sustainable, interoperable, and FAIR-aligned data infrastructures.

Finally, the team joined the National Interest Group on Open Science and Research Data Management, reinforcing its engagement with national efforts to foster knowledge sharing and alignment in the implementation of Open Science practices.

4. Next Steps

In the reporting period covering May to September 2025, several activities are planned across the GLIM-BioData project work packages. Coordination efforts will continue through regular team meetings, KPI monitoring, and active participation in GDI Consortium meetings. Outreach and visibility will be strengthened through roadshow sessions scheduled for iBET/ITQB, GiMM, and CEBAL, along with continuous updates to the project website and communications via the mailing list.

In the area of training and capacity building, the team will focus on the preparation and delivery of the first edition of the “Ready4Intensive” course on Research Data Management for Life Data (D4.1), scheduled for July 2025 and the first session of the Training Session for Data Stewards (D4.3). In parallel, preparatory work will begin for Milestone M4.1, which involves a training session dedicated to the curation and FAIR annotation of biodiversity datasets, planned for September.

Progress will also be made in WP3, with the definition of technical and operational requirements for the installation of infrastructure to manage sensitive life and health data, ensuring that all procedures align with legal, ethical, and technical standards, including GDPR compliance.

Collaboration with national RDM centres will remain a priority. The GLIM team will continue working with GBIF Portugal and FAIRway to align objectives, exchange best practices, and foster synergies within the scope of the GDI Consortium. The connection with other Health RDM Centres are being identified.

Finally, the deliverables expected to be completed or actively developed during this period include D4.1 – Ready4Intensive training course. If not yet formally submitted, D5.1 – Integration and collaboration in the national network of data stewards will also be concluded. All planned activities are in line with the project’s timeline and contribute to strengthening national capacity in research data management.